

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART VII. KINETICS OF COAGULATION OF As_2S_3 SOL WITH AND WITHOUT ADDITION OF NON-ELECTROLYTE

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The influence of non-electrolytes as studied against electrolyte coagulation has often given conflicting results even with the same sol and the same non-electrolyte. Attempts have been made to find out the influence of non-electrolytes such as methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, sugar, gelatine and agar-agar by following the kinetics of coagulation according to Smoluchowski's equation. The results reveal that methyl alcohol accelerates, whereas other non-electrolytes retard the process. This confirms the previous view that methyl alcohol sensitises the sol while other non-electrolytes protect it.

In previous communications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 25, 110) the effect of non-electrolytes on the adsorption of oppositely charged ions has been studied. It has been shown that in presence of methyl alcohol, the adsorption of oppositely charged ions decreases, whereas with ethyl alcohol, agar-agar, glucose, sucrose and gelatine, an increase in the adsorption takes place. Methyl alcohol is also known to sensitise whereas other non-electrolytes stabilise the colloid. Sensitisation or stabilisation is usually measured in terms of the quantity of electrolyte necessary to coagulate a particular quantity of the sol. Another method employed to measure sensitisation or stabilisation is to measure cataphoretic velocity of a particle of a colloid with a particular electrolyte. Mukherjee and co-workers (*Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1935, 1, 47) observed a decrease in cataphoretic velocity when sugar was added, whereas he had observed an increase in the 'chemical adsorption' (*loc. cit.*). Patel and Desai (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 51, 318) have observed a sensitising influence of sugar on thorium hydroxide sol which they subjected to progressive dialysis, whereas Mata Prasad and Nabar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 609) observed a stabilising effect of sucrose and glucose on ceric hydroxide sol. Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 668) obtained a sensitising effect of sugar on As_2S_3 sol.

The various observers thus appear to have obtained contradictory results with the same colloid (As_2S_3 sol) and the same non-electrolyte (sugar).

To us it appears that measurement of coagulation velocity of carefully purified sols in presence of pure non-electrolytes may give results which will be of use in arriving at a conclusion regarding this phenomenon.

In this paper attempts have been made to find out, if any effect is produced on the rate of coagulation of a colloid in presence of various non-electrolytes. A method similar to Paine (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1912, 4, 24) has been followed.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

As_2S_3 sol was prepared as in previous communications of this series (*loc. cit.*). The sol (5 c.c.) was taken in several bottles and the sol-electrolyte was made up to 10 c.c. in each case. Each bottle was shaken after the addition of electrolyte so as to have a homogeneous mixture and the contents filtered after 5 minutes' interval successively and the quantity of As_2S_3 left was measured by Kessler's method. In the beginning, coagulating concentration of $BaCl_2$ was determined that could coagulate As_2S_3 sol without addition of any non-electrolyte in an hour. The same concentration was used throughout irrespective of the fact that the non-electrolytes added protected or sensitised the sol. Increasing concentrations of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, sugar, agar-agar and gelatine were added to the sol and the changes in the rate of coagulation of As_2S_3 sol were determined.

The coagulation velocity constant was determined by using the formula,

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{\gamma_0}{(1 + \beta t)^2} \text{ or } \beta = \frac{1}{t} \left(\sqrt{\frac{a}{a-x}} - 1 \right)$$

and k , the bimolecular constant was also determined from the equation,

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \cdot \frac{x}{a-x}$$

To avoid complications arising out of the formation of agglomerates all observations were taken for the first thirty minutes when no visible particles were formed. We have taken the particles of original sol to be proportional to γ_0 and the concentration after a time t denoted by $a-x$, to be proportional to γ_1 . Here the uncoagulated sol is taken to consist of primary particles which are proportional to γ_1 and consequently equation $\gamma_1 = \frac{\gamma_0}{(1 + \beta t)^2}$ has been used (cf. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11). As the process followed here is the same in all the experiments, so even if there is any doubt about the concentration representing the number of particles, it is almost certain that the method gives a fair idea of the relative changes that are taking place in the sol.

The results obtained are given in the following tables and shown graphically in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

Conc. of As_2S_3 sol = 3.69 g./litre. 5 C.c. of sol + 1 c.c. of 0.01 N-BaCl₂ + 4 c.c. of distilled water.

Time.	$a-x$.	$\beta \times 10^3$ *	$k \times 10^3$.
0 min.	0.01845 g.	0.00	0.00
5	0.01537	19.12	40.07
10	0.01230	22.50	50.00
15	0.01050	21.70	50.50
20	0.00855	23.43	57.90
25	0.00740	23.16	59.70
30	0.00630	23.75	64.30

In the following tables the column $a-x$ has been omitted in order to condense the tables

TABLE II

5 C.c. sol + increasing conc. of MeOH + 1 c.c. of 0.01 N-BaCl₂ + water.
Total vol. = 10 c.c.

Time.	Volume of methyl alcohol							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	26.40	56.25	30.00	64.50	36.40	79.50	49.0	100.0
10	25.60	57.70	31.30	72.44	37.20	88.27	41.63	100.5
15	26.50	63.50	31.24	77.18	35.87	91.05	48.80	133.3
20	24.10	59.80	28.45	73.02	37.68	103.80	48.02	142.2
25	25.41	67.00	32.00	89.50	40.98	124.03	50.56	165.0
30	26.63	74.55	32.02	94.80	41.10	132.9	47.98	165.2

TABLE III

5 C.c. of As_2S_3 sol + increasing quantity of EtOH + 1 c.c. of 0.01N-BaCl₂ + the requisite amount of water to make total volume 10 c.c.

Time.	Volume of ethyl alcohol							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	16.10	33.54	14.10	29.20	9.80	15.80	11.80	24.30
10	16.60	36.67	12.05	25.50	9.80	20.60	14.40	30.85
15	17.05	38.46	12.77	27.95	9.60	20.60	13.38	29.43
20	20.45	49.20	12.79	28.80	11.25	25.05	14.75	33.87
25	18.74	46.30	14.61	34.60	11.56	26.50	14.60	34.56
30	18.61	47.60	15.20	37.60	12.18	28.80	13.63	32.80

TABLE IV

5 C.c. of As_2S_3 sol + increasing quantity of sugar + 1 c.c. of 0.01N-BaCl₂ + the requisite volume of water to make the total volume 10 c.c.

Time	Volume of 10% solution of sugar							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	15.40	32.08	7.20	14.53	6.00	12.07	4.20	8.50
10	15.60	33.70	14.40	30.85	7.22	14.95	3.90	7.90
15	17.05	38.46	11.30	24.45	6.53	13.70	3.20	6.55
20	15.36	35.40	9.79	21.50	7.20	15.43	3.61	7.50
25	16.36	39.40	9.00	20.05	7.80	17.20	4.22	8.90
30	16.07	39.87	9.67	22.08	8.53	19.23	3.65	7.70

TABLE V

5 C.c. of As_2S_3 sol + increasing quantity of gelatine (0.25%) + 0.01N-BaCl₂ + the requisite volume of water to make up the total volume 10 c.c.

Time.	Volume of gelatine (0.25%)							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	11.50	23.63	7.80	15.80	6.00	11.73	4.20	8.47
10	12.35	25.51	7.70	15.04	5.75	11.81	3.90	7.89
15	9.60	20.56	5.83	12.18	4.92	10.45	3.00	6.11
20	7.84	16.85	4.65	9.71	3.85	8.02	2.70	5.57
25	6.76	14.67	4.38	9.20	3.50	7.31	2.36	4.86
30	6.67	13.26	4.02	8.50	3.10	6.47	2.13	4.40

TABLE VI

5 C.c. of As_2S_3 sol + increasing quantity of agar-agar (0.24%) + 0.01N- $BaCl_2$ + the requisite volume of water to make up the total volume 10 c.c.

Time.	Volume of agar-agar (0.25 %)							
	1 c.c.		2 c.c.		3 c.c.		4 c.c.	
	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.	$\beta \times 10^3$.	$k \times 10^3$.
5 min.	14.10	29.20	11.50	23.63	9.60	19.64	8.68	17.70
10	14.40	30.85	9.80	20.58	8.75	18.27	7.70	16.04
15	11.30	24.44	9.30	19.95	8.03	17.01	6.53	13.73
20	9.79	24.14	8.13	17.58	7.01	16.38	5.45	11.50
25	8.40	18.57	7.28	15.91	6.24	13.48	5.27	11.25
30	7.50	16.67	6.53	14.34	5.63	12.22	4.80	10.29

DISCUSSION

From the results recorded above and shown graphically in Fig. 1, it is clear that β remains almost constant when no non-electrolyte is added. With non-electrolytes β either slightly increases (as with MeOH and sugar), or decreases (as with gelatine and agar-agar.)

In the case of methyl alcohol the β values for the same time interval increases when the concentrations of the non-electrolyte increase, whereas with other non-electrolytes β values decrease. Increase of β values with increase of methyl alcohol concentration signifies that the velocity of coagulation increases. This may be intimately connected with sensitisation, because if the stability of the colloid decreases, the velocity of coagulation will increase. In the case of other non-electrolytes *e.g.* ethyl alcohol, sugar, gelatine and agar-agar the β values decrease with increasing quantities of the non-electrolyte. This means the increase of the non-electrolytes produces more stability.

In this connection it may be noted that hitherto the action of non-electrolyte on any colloid as measured against electrolyte coagulation gave divergent results even with the same colloid and the same non-electrolyte.

Present observations on the effect of a non-electrolyte on a colloid by study of the coagulation velocity by Paine's method reveals a consistent result in so far as methyl alcohol accelerates the rate of coagulation. This acceleration is in conformity with the increase in the adsorption of oppositely charged ions by As_2S_3 sol in presence of methyl alcohol. Both these facts explain the sensitisation observed with methyl alcohol and arsenious sulphide sol. With other non-electrolytes *e.g.* ethyl alcohol, sugar, agar-agar and gelatine we find that the velocity of coagulation decreases indicating a slowing down of the coagulation process, which is in conformity with the protection observed with these non-electrolytes.

It is interesting to note that the value of β shows a slight tendency to increase with methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and sugar in the case of arsenious sulphide sol, whereas with agar-agar and gelatine it shows a distinct tendency to decrease. If in conformity with previous workers a constancy or even a slight tendency to increase in β values is taken as a characteristic property of rapid coagulation, we have to assume that arsenious sulphide sol with the addition of the non-electrolytes *e.g.*, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and sugar, maintains the character of rapid coagulation, while when gelatine and agar-agar are added to the same arsenious sulphide sol, the value of β decreases indicating that the coagulation has a tendency to become slow. Thus we see that the character of coagulation of the same sol changes gradually on the

addition of non-electrolytes. There cannot be any appreciable change in the electric charge of a colloid on adding a non-electrolyte, but the effective collisions between the particles may con

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As₂S₃ sol.

siderably decrease and thus reduce the value of ϵ , the probability factor. This suggests that ϵ may be made to change by suitably changing the concentration of the non-electrolyte in question, while the charge remains the same:

There are some discontinuities in β -time curve with MeOH and As₂S₃, whereas such discontinuities are not observable with Fe(OH)₃ sol (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 232). This may be in some way connected with the nature of the As₂S₃ sol.

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